

Supporting information to “PBTK-TD model of the phagocytosis activity in three-spined stickleback exposed to BPA”

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1. Innate immune biomarkers

Immune parameters were measured using the fish spleen which was pressed against 40 μm sterilized nylon mesh with 5 mL Leibvotitz 15 (L15) medium (Sigma) containing lithium heparin (100 mg/L, Sigma), penicillin (100 mg/L, Sigma), and streptomycin (100 mg/L, Sigma) in order to keep only the leukocytes in suspension (Bado-Nilles et al. 2014). This solution was then stored at -4°C and analysed the following day.

Innate immune biomarkers were measured from the leukocyte suspension using a MacsquantX flow cytometer (Miltenyi Biotec, Bergisch Gladbach, Germany). To compare each sample, the leukocyte concentration was normalized to 10^6 cells/ mL of culture medium.

Leukocyte sub-populations (granulocytes-macrophages), as a % of the total leukocyte population (or number of cells), was identified by their size and complexity using forward scatter (FSC) and size scatter (SSC) parameters.

Cell death was characterized by the percentage of cells in apoptosis and necrosis using a double labelling with Yo-PRO®-1 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA, final concentration: 3.14 mg/L) and propidium iodide (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA, final concentration: 5.01 mg/L) probes to obtain fluorescence of apoptotic (FL1, green fluorescence) and necrotic (FL3, red fluorescence) cells.

Leucocytes respiratory burst was also characterized (Chilmonczyk and Monge (1999)). In short, 2',7'- dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate acetyl ester (H2DCF-DA, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA, final concentration: 29.30 mg/L), a stable non-fluorescent molecule was hydrolysed to dichloro-dihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFH) by cytosolic enzymes. DCFH was then oxidized by ROS to the fluorescent dichlorofluorescein (DCF) to quantify unstimulated and cells stimulated by phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA, Sigma-Aldrich, USA, final concentration: 9.25 mg/L) in FL1. The index of respiratory burst was determined as the ratio of fluorescence of PMA stimulated cells (H2DCF-DA plus PMA) to that of unstimulated cells (H2DCF-DA).

Lysosomal presence in leukocytes were assessed using acridine orange (AO, Sigma, USA), a lysosomotropic weak base, and fluorescence measurement in FL3 (in MFI, fluorescence unit) (Bado-Nilles et al. 2013).

Finally, phagocytic activity was assessed through two parameters, leukocyte adhesion capacity and internalization efficiency, measured in % of total cells was evaluated with fluorescent microsphere at a concentration of 2.7×10^7 particles/mL (Fluorospheres® carboxylate-modified microsphere, diameter 1 μm , Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) (Gagnaire et al. 2004). Phagocytic capacity corresponded to the fluorescence of at least one bead and phagocytic efficiency to the fluorescence of at least three beads.

2. Water analysis

Water from aquariums where fish were exposed to BPA was sampled at various times and analyzed. Water from control aquariums was analyzed on the first and last day of exposure (short and long experiments). No BPA or metabolites were detected in control aquariums. Short-term exposure data are presented in table S1 for 10 µg/L nominal concentration and table S2 for 100 µg/L nominal concentration. The limit of quantification (LQ) was estimated to be 0.5, 0.35, and 0.20 ng/mL for BPA, BPA gluc, and BPA sulf. The limit of detection (LD) was estimated to be 0.3, 0.1, and 0.15 ng/mL for BPA, BPA gluc, and BPA sulf. Long-term exposure data are presented in table S3 for 100 µg/L nominal concentration of BPA.

Table S1. Measured concentrations in water (nominal concentration 10 µg/L)

	BPA (ng/ml)	BPA glu (ng/ml)	BPA sulf (ng/ml)
	Female- Male	Female- Male	Female- Male
2h	< LQ - < LQ	nd – nd	nd – nd
4h	< LQ - < LQ	nd – nd	nd – nd
8h	4.5 - 5	nd – nd	nd – nd
24h	2.2 - 5.2	nd – nd	nd – nd
48h	6.1 - 5.7	nd – nd	nd – nd
72h	6.4 - 5.8	nd – nd	nd – nd
168h	4.4 - 4.8	nd – nd	nd – nd

Table S2. Measured concentrations in water (nominal concentration 100 µg/L)

	BPA (ng/ml)	BPA glu (ng/ml)	BPA sulf (ng/ml)
	Female- Male	Female- Male	Female- Male
2h	17.3 - X	nd – nd	nd – nd
4h	23.1 – 25.4	nd – nd	nd – nd
8h	57.9 – X	nd – nd	nd – nd
24h	65.7 – 59.2	1.3 – 1.1	nd – nd
48h	64.2 – 59.6	1.5 – 1.5	nd – nd
72h	66.8 – 64.7	0.8 – 0.8	nd – nd
168h	70.1 – 65.9	2.3 – 1.4	nd – nd

Table S3. Measured concentrations in water (nominal concentration 100 µg/L)

	BPA (ng/ml)
	Female- Male
Day 1	53.2-57.2
Day 3	53.7-60.2
Day 8	47.2-64.2
Day 15	67.8-49.7
Day 21	49.3-58.6

Table S7. Measured concentrations in male stickleback blood

Sample	[BPA] (ng/g)		[BPA-Sulf] (ng/g)		[BPA-Gluc] (ng/g)	
	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
Nominal concentration	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
DAY 0.25	< LQ	122,7	0,2	8,6	32,5	961,7
DAY 1	11,4	Analytical issue	1,5	Analytical issue	91,3	Analytical issue
DAY 4	17,6	84,8	1,0	10,4	155,4	1460,1
DAY 7	9,9	77,4	1,0	9,6	124,4	1478,4
DAY 8	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	1,2	15,3	218,0
DAY 14	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	21,5

Table S8. Measured concentrations in female stickleback dried carcass

Sample	[BPA] (ng/g)		[BPA-Sulf] (ng/g)		[BPA-Gluc] (ng/g)	
	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
Nominal concentration	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
DAY 0.25	< LQ	313,0	1,1	5,5	32,5	499,8
DAY 1	40,2	2634,1	3,1	63,0	252,9	2134,9
DAY 4	43,9	853,1	1,5	22,0	288,5	1460,8
DAY 7	51,1	369,7	2,5	13,3	194,5	2454,7
DAY 8	< LQ	113,9	< LQ	11,0	35,7	507,9
DAY 14	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	3,5	23,0	15,7

Table S9. Measured concentrations in male stickleback dried carcass

Sample	[BPA] (ng/g)		[BPA-Sulf] (ng/g)		[BPA-Gluc] (ng/g)	
	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
Nominal concentration	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
DAY 0.25	< LQ	498,5	< LQ	14,8	60,1	617,6
DAY 1	36,6	1825,8	1	49,0	57,8	3993,4
DAY 4	34,3	1403,5	3,8	35,4	210,6	1253,3
DAY 7	45,2	639,3	2	52,6	82,6	1609,7
DAY 8	< LQ	< LQ	1,3	4,4	51,3	74,3
DAY 14	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	< LQ	23,2	19,8

4. Simulated concentrations in richly perfused tissues

The PBPK presented in Mit et al., 2022 allowed to predict BPA and BPA metabolites in stickleback organs over time by taking measured water concentrations over time as inputs. Then, the toxicodynamic part of the model took as inputs the concentrations of BPA and BPA metabolites in richly perfused tissues (RPT) (used as a proxy for the spleen where immunomarkers were measured). In Table S10, predicted concentrations in RPT for a male stickleback are presented.

Table S10. Predicted concentrations in male stickleback richly perfused tissues

Nominal concentration	[BPA] (ng/g)		[BPA-Sulf] (ng/g)		[BPA-Gluc] (ng/g)	
	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L	10 µg/L	100 µg/L
DAY 0.25	2.32	27.7	0.08	0.93	6.75	73.7
DAY 1	3.93	45.0	0.41	4.68	26.4	297.9
DAY 4	4.40	49.0	0.62	6.65	35.3	378.0
DAY 7	3.70	50.0	0.54	6.93	30.1	391.4
DAY 8	0.19	0.23	0.14	1.48	5.13	49.0
DAY 14	0.19	0.19	0.02	0.02	1.53	1.49

5. Statistical analysis

Prior to modelling, a statistical analysis was performed on each immunomarker response over time. All responses were log-transformed. At each date, a one-way ANOVA followed by a post-hoc Dunnett test was used to determine if a true difference existed between conditions and control. Then, the biomarkers presenting the most consistent response over time were selected to be modelled.

5.1. Leucocyte distribution (Figure 2)

Leucocyte distribution - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment				Time (d)	Long Experiment					
		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)						
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.11891	0.06825	-1.742	0.154404	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.28108	0.07120	-3.948	0.000452 ***						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.07383	0.07282	-1.014	0.495	Day 14	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.06044	0.07198	0.840	0.610						
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.08432	0.07614	1.107	0.441	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.06028	0.07823	-0.771	0.662						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.14604	0.09822	-1.487	0.2442						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.22151	0.09950	-2.226	0.0553 .						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.1408	0.1105	-1.274	0.3442						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.2338	0.1105	-2.115	0.0707 .						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.19619	0.07515	-2.611	0.0218 *						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.17917	0.07613	-2.353	0.0411 *						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

5.2. Cellular mortality (Figure 3)

Cellular mortality - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment				Time (d)	Long Experiment					
		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)						
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.07194	0.16293	0.442	0.870	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.16639	0.16997	0.979	0.523						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.1547	0.1278	1.210	0.37681	Day 14	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.3876	0.1263	3.068	0.00631 **						
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.19547	0.18659	1.048	0.478	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.07584	0.19171	-0.396	0.894						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.21832	0.16991	1.285	0.339						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.09178	0.17213	0.533	0.816						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.04079	0.17550	0.232	0.961						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.26845	0.17550	1.530	0.226						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.3183	0.1544	2.061	0.0799 .						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.3440	0.1565	2.199	0.0588 .						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

5.3. Phagocytic activity (Figure 4)

Splenic immune phagocytosis capacity - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment				Time (d)	Long Experiment					
		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)						
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.03539	0.04533	0.781	0.656	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.01704	0.04729	0.360	0.911						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.07160	0.03190	2.245	0.0525 .	Day 14	Linear Hypotheses:				
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.07271	0.03152	2.307	0.0455 *		BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.009290	0.024258	-0.383	0.899	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.003981	0.024567	-0.162	0.981						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.00671	0.03179	0.211	0.968						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.02656	0.03220	0.825	0.624						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.009674	0.022386	0.432	0.8737						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.059799	0.022386	2.671	0.0186 *						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.0005394	0.0210658	0.026	1.000						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.0385426	0.0213411	-1.806	0.135						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

Splenic immune phagocytosis efficiency - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment					Time (d)	Long Experiment				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.11062	0.08295	1.334	0.3162	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	0.35585	0.07569	4.702	< 1e-04 ***
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.17986	0.08653	2.079	0.0775 .						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.11571	0.08033	1.44	0.26183	Day 14	BPA - Control == 0	0.15595	0.08165	1.910	0.148
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.24052	0.07939	3.03	0.00703 **						
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.04458	0.07306	0.610	0.766	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	-0.08321	0.06929	-1.201	0.488
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.08891	0.07399	1.202	0.383						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.11816	0.05628	2.099	0.0735 .						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.29615	0.05702	5.194	5.92e-06 ***						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.10013	0.07246	1.382	0.29034						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.30513	0.07246	4.211	0.00018 ***						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.08029	0.05256	1.528	0.228						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.04283	0.05324	0.804	0.638						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

5.4. Splenic lysosomal presence (Figure 5)

Splenic lysosomal presence - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment					Time (d)	Long Experiment				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.4305	0.1188	3.623	0.00126 **	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	0.04535	0.05625	0.806	0.75976
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.7662	0.1240	6.181	1.74e-07 ***						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.008383	0.078878	0.106	0.991634	Day 14	BPA - Control == 0	0.06428	0.11646	0.552	0.90314
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.320208	0.077958	4.107	0.000254 ***						
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.02615	0.07975	0.328	0.9253	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	-0.10735	0.06184	-1.736	0.206
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.18898	0.08194	2.306	0.0461 *						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.2265	0.1103	2.053	0.081310 .						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.4487	0.1118	4.014	0.000353 ***						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.26226	0.08447	3.105	0.005699 **						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.33995	0.08447	4.025	0.000334 ***						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.15117	0.09552	1.583	0.20644						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.35552	0.09677	3.674	0.00105 **						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

5.5. Respiratory burst (Figure 6)

Inactivated ROS level (MFI) - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment					Time (d)	Long Experiment				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.2163	0.2537	0.852	0.607	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	1.0180	0.1384	7.357	1.59e-10 ***
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.3789	0.2647	1.432	0.270						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.3574	0.1197	2.986	0.00793 **	Day 14	BPA - Control == 0	1.5816	0.2341	6.755	<1e-08 ***
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.9435	0.1183	7.977	1.5e-10 ***						
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.1340	0.1189	1.127	0.429	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	0.9139	0.1293	7.068	1.11e-09 ***
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.6753	0.1222	5.526	1.85e-06 ***						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.6234	0.1813	3.438	0.00216 **						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	1.3647	0.1790	7.626	6.4e-10 ***						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.2383	0.1335	1.785	0.140748						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.5465	0.1335	4.094	0.000266 ***						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.8298	0.1560	5.320	3.75e-06 ***						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	1.5300	0.1580	9.683	< 1e-10 ***						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

Respiratory burst index - Multiple Comparisons of Means: Dunnett Contrasts											
Time (d)	Short experiment					Time (d)	Long Experiment				
	Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		Estimate	Std. Error	t value	Pr(> t)		
Day 0.25	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.2977	0.2358	1.263	0.3529	Day 7	BPA - Control == 0	-0.56271	0.08483	-6.634	<1e-08 ***
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.6506	0.2460	2.645	0.0202 *						
Day 1	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.4171	0.1832	2.276	0.0488 *	Day 14	BPA - Control == 0	-0.4959	0.2015	-2.461	0.0432 *
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.3287	0.1811	1.815	0.1319						
Day 4	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.5306	0.1168	4.541	6.12e-05 ***	Day 21	BPA - Control == 0	-0.11213	0.08573	-1.308	0.41964
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.2281	0.1200	1.900	0.113						
Day 7	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.5310	0.2150	-2.470	0.031 *						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.2999	0.2122	-1.413	0.276						
Day 8	BPA10 - Control == 0	0.4447	0.1106	4.021	0.000339 ***						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	0.4697	0.1106	4.246	0.000160 ***						
Day 14	BPA10 - Control == 0	-0.07104	0.12247	-0.580	0.787						
	BPA100 - Control == 0	-0.14071	0.12407	-1.134	0.424						

Signif. codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1 (Adjusted p values reported -- single-step method)

6. MCMC calibration

6.1. Parametrization

Calibration was carried out using GNU MCSim v6.2.0 (Bois 2009). Prior distributions are described in Table 2. Data likelihoods are available in section 7. Model code. MCSim gives the possibility to specify a distribution for the data. The probability of realization of modeled outputs was then described with LogNormal distribution with a variation coefficient which was calibrated to consider inter-individual variability (parameter “sigma” Table S4).

6.2. Calibration results

Parameters were calibrated using Monte Carlo Markov Chains, with three chains of 20 000 iterations each. Convergence was assessed in R 3.6.1 (R Core Team 2019) with the package coda by checking that autocorrelations were low (i.e., that the chains were well mixed), that estimates lay well within the prior boundaries, and that the Gelman-Rubin index was close to 1.

Table S11. Summary of posterior distributions for the estimated parameters of the TD model.

Outputs	Parameters	Prior		Posterior : MPV [IC 95%]	
Lysosomal presence	K_{in}	Uniform	[0 ; 1000 [705.5	[508.0 ; 994.4]
	K_{out}	Uniform	[0 ; 1000 [3.32	[2.39 ; 4.68]
	S_{max_lyso}	$N(\mu=1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [1.81	[0.93 ; 2.59]
	SC_{50_lyso}	$N(\mu=0.2, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [0.216	[0.109 ; 0.316]
	K_{toL_lyso}	$N(\mu=0.1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [0.105	[0.050 ; 0.163]
	kr_delay	$N(\mu=1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [0.989	[0.422 ; 1.58]
	τ	$N(\mu=8, CV=30\%)$	[7 ; 13]	7.93	[7.08 ; 12.08]
	Σ	$N(\mu=2, CV=30\%)$	[1 ; 10 [1.16	[1.13 ; 1.37]
Phagocytic efficiency	K_{in}	Uniform	[0 ; 1000 [978.7	[256.5 ; 991.0]
	K_{out}	Uniform	[0 ; 1000 [37.42	[9.8 ; 39.8]
	K_{toL_phago}	$N(\mu=1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; 1000 [0.860	[0.337 ; 1.471]
	S_{max_phago}	$N(\mu=0.2, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [0.277	[0.201 ; 0.36]
	SC_{50_phago}	$N(\mu=0.1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [0.0983	[0.0399 ; 0.154]
	kr_delay	$N(\mu=1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [1.01	[0.50 ; 1.62]
	τ	$N(\mu=11, CV=10\%)$	[0 ; 22]	12.3	[9.56 ; 13.3]
	Σ	$N(\mu=2, CV=30\%)$	[1 ; 10 [1.10	[1.1 ; 1.14]
Inactivated ROS	K_{in}	Uniform	[0 ; 1000 [727.1	[200.4 ; 987.1]
	K_{out}	Uniform	[0 ; 1000 [65.3	[18.1 ; 100.1]
	S_{max_rosb}	$N(\mu=1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [1.43	[0.95 ; 1.84]
	SC_{50_rosb}	$N(\mu=0.1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [0.10	[0.045 ; 0.159]
	kr_delay	$N(\mu=1, CV=30\%)$	[0 ; +∞ [1.05	[0.50 ; 1.58]
	τ	$N(\mu=2, CV=10\%)$	[0 ; 22 [2.00	[1.60 ; 2.39]
		Σ	$N(\mu=2, CV=30\%)$	[1 ; 10 [1.43

- Sigma is the geometric standard deviation (exponential, strictly superior to 1, of the standard deviation in log-space) of the lognormal distribution of the data, given the model

Table S12. Model performances (RMSE, mean fold, BIC) for the phagocytic internalization efficiency by backward selection starting from the model with delay and control loop (Equation 6).

phagocytic internalization efficiency	RMSE	Mean fold	BIC	Equation
Delay and control loop (Equation 6)	0.104	1.079	-34.1	$\frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{S_{max} \times D_{art\ glu}}{SC_{50} + D_{art\ glu}} \right) \times \frac{1}{M} - K_{out} \times R$
without delay (Equation 7)	0.100	1.076	-38.7	$\frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{S_{max} \times C_{art\ glu}}{SC_{50} + C_{art\ glu}} \right) \times \frac{1}{M} - K_{out} \times R$
without control loop	0.128	1.093	-22.0	$\frac{dR}{dt} = K_{in} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{S_{max} \times D_{art\ glu}}{SC_{50} + D_{art\ glu}} \right) - K_{out} \times R$

7. Informatic model code (Mcsim 6.2.0)

7.1. Model file for phagocytosis (efficiency)

```
#####AUTHOR : CORENTIN MIT
=====
# (I.) INFORMATIONS
=====
#####
# MODEL BPA
# BASE : VIDAL - GRECH
# VERSION: PBTK TD
# UPDATE : MECHANISM-BASED INDIRECT DELAYED RESPONSE (1 PARAMETER) WITH FEEDBACK
# DATE : 05/09/2022
#####
### UNITS:
###
# QUANTITY          MICROG
# VOLUMES:          ML
# TIME:             DAY
# FLOWS:            ML/D
# CONCENTRATIONS:  MICROG/ML OR MICROG/G
# VMAX:             MICROG/D/ ML LIVER OR MICROG/D/ G LIVER
# KM:              MICROG/ML
# MASSES:          G
# LENGHT:          MM
# TEMPERATURE:     CELSIUS
# VENTILATION RATE: ML/D
# DENSITY OF EACH TISSUE IS CONSIDERED EQUAL TO 1
#####

=====
# (II.) MODEL VARIABLES
=====

#
# STATES
#

STATES = {

  L,                                     # STRUCTURAL LENGTH

  #Q_WATER,                               # QUANTITY OF BPA IN WATER (MICROG)
  Q_ART,                                  # QUANTITY OF BPA IN ARTERIAL BLOOD (MICROG)
  Q_VEN,                                  # QUANTITY BPA IN VENOUS BLOOD (MICROG)
  Q_VISCERA,                              # ... BPA IN VISCERA (MICROG)
  Q_LUMEN_GIT,                            # ... BPA IN LUMEN (MICROG)
  Q_GONADS,                               # ... BPA IN GONADS (MICROG)
  Q_KIDNEY,                               # ... BPA IN KIDNEY (MICROG)
  Q_LIVER,                                # ... BPA IN LIVER (MICROG)
  Q_SKIN,                                 # ... BPA IN SKIN (MICROG)
  Q_BRAIN,                                # ... BPA IN BRAIN (MICROG)
  Q_FAT,                                  # ... BPA IN FAT (MICROG)
  Q_PP,                                   # ... BPA IN POORLY PERFUSED (MICROG)
  Q_RP,                                   # ... BPA IN RICHLY PERFUSED (MICROG)

  Q_ADMIN_GILLS,                          # ... BPA ENTERING THROUGH GILLS (MICROG)
  Q_MET,                                  # ... BPA METABOLIZED IN TOTAL (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET_FECES,                         # ... BPA FECALLY EXCRETED (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET_GILLS,                         # ... BPA EXCRETED BY GILLS (MICROG)
  Q_BILE,                                  # ... BPA IN BILIARY VESICULE (MICROG)
  Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO,                      # ... BPA METABOLIZED IN BPAG IN LIVER (MICROG)
  Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO,                      # ... BPA METABOLIZED IN BPAS IN LIVER (MICROG)
  Q_MET_PLASMA_GLUCO,                     # ... BPA METABOLIZED IN BPAG IN PLASMA (MICROG)
  Q_MET_PLASMA_SULFO,                     # ... BPA METABOLIZED IN BPAG IN PLASMA (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET,                               # TOTAL OF BPA QUANTITY EXCRETED (MICROG)

  # Q_WATER_GLUCO,                        # QUANTITY OF BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN WATER (MICROG)
  Q_ART_GLUCO,                            # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN ARTERIAL BLOOD (MICROG)
  Q_VEN_GLUCO,                            # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN VENOUS BLOOD (MICROG)
  Q_LUMEN_GIT_GLUCO, # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN LUMEN (MICROG))
  Q_LIVER_GLUCO,                          # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN LIVER (MICROG))
  Q_GONADS_GLUCO,                         # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN GONADS (MICROG))
  Q_ROB_GLUCO,                            # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN REST OF BODY (MICROG))
  Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_GLUCO, # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN KIDNEY AND VISCERA (MICROG))

  Q_EXCRET_GILLS_GLUCO,                   # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES EXCRETED BY GILLS (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET_FECES_GLUCO,                   # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES FECALLY EXCRETED (MICROG)
  Q_BILE_GLUCO,                           # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN BILIARY VESICULE (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET_GLUCO,                         # TOTAL OF BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES QUANTITY EXCRETED (MICROG)

  #Q_WATER_SULFO,                         # QUANTITY OF BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN WATER (MICROG)
  Q_ART_SULFO,                            # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN ARTERIAL BLOOD (MICROG)
  Q_VEN_SULFO,                            # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN VENOUS BLOOD (MICROG)
  Q_LUMEN_GIT_SULFO, # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN LUMEN (MICROG))
  Q_LIVER_SULFO,                          # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN LIVER (MICROG))
  Q_GONADS_SULFO,                         # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN GONADS (MICROG))
  Q_ROB_SULFO,                            # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN REST OF BODY (MICROG))
  Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_SULFO, # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN KIDNEY AND VISCERA (MICROG))

  Q_EXCRET_GILLS_SULFO,                   # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES EXCRETED BY GILLS (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET_FECES_SULFO,                   # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES FECALLY EXCRETED (MICROG)
  Q_BILE_SULFO,                           # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN BILIARY VESICULE (MICROG)
  Q_EXCRET_SULFO,                         # TOTAL OF BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES QUANTITY EXCRETED (MICROG)

  #TOXICODYNAMICS
  RESPONSE_PHAGO_PERCENT,                 #PHAGOCYTOSIS RESPONSE (FRACTION %)
```

```

RESPONSE_LYSO,      #LYSOSOMAL PRESENCE RESPONSE (MFI)
RESPONSE_MACRO_PERCENT, #GRANULOCYTES-MACROPHAGES RESPONSE (FRACTION %)
RESPONSE_TBARS,    #TBARS RESPONSE(NMOL MDA/G PROT)
RESPONSE_ROSA,

M_TBARS, #MODERATOR
M_MACRO, #MODERATOR
M_LYSO,
M_ROSA,
DELAY,
};

#=====
#          OUTPUTS
#=====

OUTPUTS = {

C_ART,      # ... BPA      IN ARTERIAL BLOOD (MICROG.ML-1)
C_BRAIN, # ... BPA      IN BRAIN (MICROG.ML-1)
C_VEN,     # ... BPA      IN VENOUS BLOOD (MICROG.ML-1)
C_VISCERA, # ... BPA      IN VISCERA (MICROG.ML-1)
C_GONADS, # ... BPA      IN GONADS (MICROG.ML-1)
C_LIVER,  # ... BPA      IN LIVER (MICROG.ML-1)
C_SKIN,   # ... BPA      IN SKIN (MICROG.ML-1)
C_FAT,    # ... BPA      IN FAT (MICROG.ML-1)
C_PP,     # ... BPA      IN PP (MICROG.ML-1)
C_RP,     # ... BPA      IN RP (MICROG.ML-1)
C_CARASS, # ... BPA      IN CARCASS (MICROG.ML-1)
C_TOT,    # ... BPA      IN TOTAL (MICROG.ML-1)
C_TOT_BILE, # TOTAL CONCENTRATION IN FISH OF BPA INCLUDING THE QUANTITY IN BILIARY VESICULE (MICROG.ML-1)

Q_ADMIN_TOT, # ... BPA      ABSORBED IN TOTAL (MICROG)
Q_ELIM_TOT, # ... BPA      ELIMINATED IN TOTAL (MICROG)
Q_BODY,     # TOTAL OF BPA QUANTITY IN FISH BODY (MICROG)

# C_WATER_GLUCCO,      # CONCENTRATION OF BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN WATER (MICROG.ML-1)
C_ART_GLUCCO,      # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN ARTERIAL BLOOD (MICROG.ML-1)
C_VEN_GLUCCO,     # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN VENOUS BLOOD (MICROG.ML-1)
C_GONADS_GLUCCO, # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN GONADS (MICROG.ML-1)
C_LIVER_GLUCCO,  # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN LIVER (MICROG.ML-1)
C_ROB_GLUCCO,    # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN REST OF FISH BODY (MICROG.ML-1)
C_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCCO, # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN KIDNEY AND VISCERA (MICROG)
C_TOT_GLUCCO,    # ... BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES IN FISH BODY (MICROG.ML-1)
C_TOT_BILE_GLUCCO, # TOTAL CONCENTRATION OF BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES INCLUDING THE QUANTITY IN BILIARY VESICULE.

# C_WATER_SULFO,      # CONCENTRATION OF BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN WATER (MICROG.ML-1)
C_ART_SULFO,      # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN ARTERIAL BLOOD (MICROG.ML-1)
C_VEN_SULFO,     # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN VENOUS BLOOD (MICROG.ML-1)
C_GONADS_SULFO, # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN GONADS (MICROG.ML-1)
C_LIVER_SULFO,  # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN LIVER (MICROG.ML-1)
C_ROB_SULFO,    # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN REST OF FISH BODY (MICROG.ML-1)
C_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO, # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN KIDNEY AND VISCERA (MICROG)
C_TOT_SULFO,    # ... BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES IN FISH BODY (MICROG.ML-1)
C_TOT_BILE_SULFO, # TOTAL CONCENTRATION IN FISH OF BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATES INCLUDING THE QUANTITY IN BILIARY
VESICULE.

#NEEDED TO CALIBRATE EXCRETION IN LINDHOLST 2003
C_TOT_PC,      # RATIO OF BPA CONCENTRATION AT TIME T AND AT 7D
C_TOT_GLUCCO_PC, # RATIO OF BPAG CONCENTRATION AT TIME T AND AT 7D
C_TOT_SULFO_PC, # RATIO OF BPAS CONCENTRATION AT TIME T AND AT 7D

C_TOT_LIND,      # SAVE CONCENTRATIONS OF BPA AT T = 7D
C_TOT_GLUCCO_LIND, # SAVE CONCENTRATIONS OF BPAG AT T = 7D
C_TOT_SULFO_LIND, # SAVE CONCENTRATIONS OF BPAS AT T = 7D

# VARIABLES COMPUTED TO EVALUATE THE MODEL
MASS_BAL,      # MASS BALANCE (MICROG.ML-1)
# MASS_BAL_SYS, # MASS BALANCE INCLUDING QUANTITY IN AQUARIUM (MICROG.ML-1)
MASS_BAL_GLUCCO, # MASS BALANCE OF BPA-GLUCURONIDE CONJUGATES (MICROG.ML-1)
MASS_BAL_SULFO, # MASS BALANCE OF BPA-SULFATE CONJUGATE (MICROG.ML-1)
BW,            # FISH BODY MASS (G)
LENGTH,       # PHYSICAL TOTAL LENGTH (MM)

#OTHER VARIABLES
C_BISPENOL,    # CONCENTRATION OF BISPENOL ALL FORMS TAKE INTO ACCOUNT.

#TOXICODYNAMICS
RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT, #CALIBRATION
RATIO_TBARS,
RATIO_MACRO_PERCENT, #CALIBRATION
RATIO_LYSO,
RATIO_ROSA,
#M_PHAGO, #MODERATOR
};

#=====
#          INPUTS
#=====

INPUTS = {
TEMPERATURE, # WATER TEMPERATURE EXPRESSED IN DEGREE CELSIUS
C_WATER,     # CONCENTRATION OF BPA CHEMICAL IN WATER (MICROG.ML-1)
V_WATER,     # VOLUME OF AQUARIUM (ML)
BW_I,        # INITIAL MASS OF FISH (G)
IVQUANTITY, # INTRAVENOUS QUANTITY (µG)
F_CST,      # FOOD LEVEL 1 = AD-LIBITUM, 0= STARVATION
EVENT_BILE; #<INPUT VARIABLE> = NDoses (<N>, <LIST-OF-MAGNITUDES>, <LIST-OF-INITIAL-TIMES>);
};

#=====

```

```

# (III) MODEL PARAMETERS
#=====
#-----
# PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS
#-----
BW_FCARD_REF      ;# BODY WEIGHT OF REFERENCE FOR F_CARD
BW_VO2_REF        ;# BODY WEIGHT OF REFERENCE FOR VO2 FROM MACLEOD, 1996
DEB_V             ;# ENERGY CONDUCTANCE (MM/D) (DEB MODEL PARAMETER)
DEB_G             ;# ENERGY INVESTMENT RATIO (SU) (DEB MODEL PARAMETER)
DEB_KM           ;# SOMATIC MAINTENANCE RATE COEFFICIENT (1/D) (DEB MODEL PARAMETER)
DEB_EHM          ;# ENERGY AT STATE OF MATURITY AT METAMORPHOSIS (J)
DEB_EHB          ;# ENERGY AT STATE OF MATURITY AT BIRTH (J)
DEB_SHAPE        ;
A_BW_L           ;# A RELATION BW(G)=F(L(CM))
B_BW_L           ;# B RELATION BW(G)=F(L(CM))

#-----
# ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION
#-----
TA               ;# ARRHENIUS TEMPERATURE IN KELVIN
TR_EXCRETION    ;# ARRHENIUS REFERENCE TEMPERATURE FOR THE EXCRETION PROCESSES (KELVIN)
TR_DEB          ;# ARRHENIUS REFERENCE TEMPERATURE FOR THE DEB MODEL (KELVIN)
TR_FCARD        ;# ARRHENIUS REFERENCE TEMPERATURE FOR CARDIAC OUTPUT (KELVIN) -> TEMPERATURE OPTIMAL : 25 C
TR_VO2          ;# ARRHENIUS REFERENCE TEMPERATURE FOR REPSIRATION (KELVIN)

#-----
# EFFECTIVE RESPIRATORY VOLUME & CARDIAC OUTPUT
#-----
F_CARD_REF ;# QB_REF_RT * (BW_REF^(0.75)) / BW_REF # (ML/D/G) = 28.5 * (7.66^(0.75)) / 7.66 --> ALLOMETRIC SCALLING

FUNCTION
V_O2_REF ;# REFERENCE OXYGEN COMSUPTION RATE (MG/KG/MIN) --> 2.236044 * 60 * 24 / 1000 MG/G/D FROM MACLEOD, 1966
O2_EE    ;# OXYGEN EXTRACTION EFFICIENCY OF 71% PROPOSED BY ERICKSON, 1990
SAT      ;# DISSOLVED OXYGEN SATURATION OF 90% PROPOSED BY ERICKSON, 1990
FRAC_ART_VEN = (1.0/3.0); # FRACTION OF ARTERIAL BLOOD

#-----
# VOLUME SCALING FACTOR : FRACTION OF BW (%)
#-----
SC_BLOOD ;# VOLUME SCALING FACTOR, EXPRESSED IN % BW (G)
SC_GONADS ;
SC_BRAIN ;
SC_LIVER ;
SC_FAT ;
SC_SKIN ;
SC_VISCERA ;
SC_KIDNEY ;
SC_RP ;
SC_PP ;

#-----
# FRACTION OF ARTERIAL BLOOD FLOW
#-----
FRAC_GONADS ;# FRACTION OF ARTERIAL BLOOD FLOW
FRAC_BRAIN ;
FRAC_LIVER ;
FRAC_FAT ;
FRAC_SKIN ;
FRAC_VISCERA ;
FRAC_KIDNEY ;
FRAC_RP ;
FRAC_PP ;

A_FPP = 0.4 ;# FRACTION OF PPT BLOOD GOING TO VENOUS
A_FS = 0.1 ;# FRACTION OF SKIN BLOOD GOING TO VENOUS

PLASMA ;# PLASMA FRACTION 1 - HAEMATOCRIT

#-----
# EXPOSURE QUANTITY (MICROG)
#-----
WATERQUANTITY ;
IVQUANTITY ;

#-----
# CHEMICAL PARAMETERS
#-----
UNBOUND_FRACTION ; # BETWEEN 0 AND 1
UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO ; # BETWEEN 0 AND 1
UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO ; # BETWEEN 0 AND 1

#-----
# PARTITION COEFFICIENT (PC QSAR IN .R, NEED ADAPTATION TO ORGAN COMPOSITIONS )
#-----
PC_BLOOD_WATER ; # PARTITION COEF BLOOD WATER FOR BPA
PC_LIVER ; # PARTITION COEF LIVER ""
PC_GONADS ; # PARTITION COEF GONADE ""
PC_VISCERA ; # PARTITION COEF VISCERA ""
PC_FAT ; # PARTITION COEF FAT FOR ""
PC_KIDNEY ; # PARTITION COEF KIDNEY ""
PC_SKIN ; # PARTITION COEF SKIN ""
PC_BRAIN ; # PARTITION COEF BRAIN ""
PC_RP ; # PARTITION COEF RP ""
PC_PP ; # PARTITION COEF PP ""

#PC_BLOOD_WATER_GLUCO ; # PARTITION COEF BLOOD WATER FOR BPA-G
PC_LIVER_GLUCO ;
PC_GONADS_GLUCO ;
PC_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO ;
PC_ROB_GLUCO ;

#PC_BLOOD_WATER_SULFO ; # PARTITION COEF BLOOD WATER FOR BPA-S
PC_LIVER_SULFO ;

```

```

PC_GONADS_SULFO ;
PC_ABDU_CAVITY_SULFO ;
PC_ROB_SULFO ;

#-----
# METABOLISM (BASED ON PROT.TOT IN STICKLEBACK)
#-----

KM_GLUCO ; # MICROG/ML #OHKIMOTO 2003
VMAX_GLUCO ; # MICROG/D/ML LIVER #OHKIMOTO 2003

KM_SULFO ; # MICROG/ML #OHKIMOTO 2003
VMAX_SULFO ; # MICROG/D/ML LIVER #OHKIMOTO 2003

#CL_LIVER_GLUCO ; # ML/D/G LIVER
#CL_LIVER_SULFO ; # ML/D/G LIVER

CL_PLASMA_GLUCO ; # ML/D/ML BLOOD
CL_PLASMA_SULFO ; # ML/D/ML BLOOD

#-----
# EXCRETION
#-----

K_BG ; # EXCRETED FLOW FROM BILLIARY VESICULE TO FAECES (1/D)
KE_BILE ; # EXCRETED FLOW OF BPA FROM LIVER TO BILLIARY VESICULE (1/D)
KE_BILE_GLUCO ; # EXCRETED FLOW OF BPA-G FROM LIVER TO BILLIARY VESICULE (1/D)
KE_BILE_SULFO ; # EXCRETED FLOW OF BPA-S FROM LIVER TO BILLIARY VESICULE (1/D)

#-----
# FECES AND URINATION
#-----
KE_FECES = 0.83 ; # 1/D ESTIMATED FROM NICHOLS ET AL. 2004
URINE_RATE = 0.05794769 ; # V_BURST = 1.2 ML.KG-1 EVERY 29.82 MINUTES PROPOSED BY CURTIS 1991 --> 1.2E-03 ML.G BW-

#-----
# TOXICODYNAMIC
#-----

#PHAGOCYTOSIS
K_IN_PHAGO ; #FRACTION GAIN*D-1
K_OUT_PHAGO ; #D-1
S_MAX_PHAGO ;
SC_50_PHAGO ; #µG/ML
R0_PHAGO ;
K_TOL_PHAGO;
KR_DELAY;
TAU;
#MACROPHAGES
K_IN_MACRO ; #FRACTION GAIN*D-1
K_OUT_MACRO ; #D-1
EC_50_MACRO ; #µG/ML
K_TOL_MACRO;
R0_MACRO ;

#LYSOSOME
K_IN_LYSO ; #FRACTION GAIN*D-1
K_OUT_LYSO ; #D-1
S_MAX_LYSO ;
SC_50_LYSO ; #µG/ML
R0_LYSO ;
K_TOL_LYSO;

#TBARS
K_IN_TBARS ; #FRACTION GAIN*D-1
K_OUT_TBARS ; #D-1
S_MAX_TBARS ;
SC_50_TBARS ; #µG/ML
R0_TBARS ;
K_TOL_TBARS;
#ROSA
K_IN_ROSA ; #FRACTION GAIN*D-1
K_OUT_ROSA ; #D-1
S_MAX_ROSA ;
SC_50_ROSA ; #µG/ML
R0_ROSA ;
K_TOL_ROSA ;

#-----
# OTHER PARAMETERS THAT WILL BE COMPUTED IN INITIALIZE
#-----
CONV_GLUCO = (404/228.29); # RATIO MOLAR MASS BPA-G/BPA
CONV_SULFO = (308/228.29); # RATIO MOLAR MASS BPA-S/BPA
WATER_CONTENT_BLOOD ; # BERTELSEN 1998 IN TROUT
C_TOT_LIND ; #µG/G
C_TOT_GLUCO_LIND ; #µG/G
C_TOT_SULFO_LIND ; #µG/G
ABS_EFF ; #GILLS ABSORPTION EFFICIENCY (0-1)
RATIO_PC_UF;
RATIO_VMAX_KM_GLUCO;
RATIO_VMAX_KM_SULFO;
SIGMA_C_MACRO;
SIGMA_C_LYSO;
SIGMA_C_ROSA;
SIGMA_C_PHAGO;

#-----
# (IV) MODEL INITIALIZATION
#-----

INITIALIZE {
SC_PP = (1 - SC_BLOOD - SC_GONADS - SC_BRAIN - SC_LIVER - SC_FAT

```

```

- SC_SKIN - SC_VISCERA - SC_KIDNEY -SC_RP);

FRAC_PP = (1 - FRAC_GONADS - FRAC_BRAIN - FRAC_LIVER - FRAC_FAT
- FRAC_SKIN - FRAC_VISCERA - FRAC_KIDNEY - FRAC_RP);

Q_VEN = IVQUANTITY;

L = POW((BW_I/ A_BW_L), (1/B_BW_L)) * DEB_SHAPE * 10;

PC_BLOOD_WATER = UNBOUND_FRACTION * RATIO_PC_UF ;
#PC_BLOOD_WATER_GLUCO = UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO * RATIO_PC_UF_GLUCO ;
#PC_BLOOD_WATER_SULFO = UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO * RATIO_PC_UF_SULFO ;

VMAX_GLUCO = KM_GLUCO * RATIO_VMAX_KM_GLUCO ;
VMAX_SULFO = KM_SULFO * RATIO_VMAX_KM_SULFO ;

#-----
#TOXICODYNAMICS
#-----

#PHAGOCYTOSIS
RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT = 1.0;
RESPONSE_PHAGO_PERCENT = R0_PHAGO ;
DELAY = 0.0;

#MACROPHAGES
M_MACRO = R0_MACRO;
RATIO_MACRO_PERCENT = 1.0;
RESPONSE_MACRO_PERCENT = R0_MACRO ;
K_IN_MACRO = POW(R0_MACRO,2) * K_OUT_MACRO ;

#LYSOSOMES
M_LYSO = R0_LYSO;
RATIO_LYSO = 1.0;
RESPONSE_LYSO = R0_LYSO ;
K_IN_LYSO = R0_LYSO * K_OUT_LYSO ;

#TBARS
M_TBARS = R0_TBARS;
RATIO_TBARS = 1.0;
RESPONSE_TBARS = R0_TBARS ;
K_IN_TBARS = POW(R0_TBARS,2) * K_OUT_TBARS ;

#ROS A
M_ROSA = R0_ROSA;
RATIO_ROSA = 1.0;
RESPONSE_ROSA = R0_ROSA ;
K_IN_ROSA = POW(R0_ROSA,2) * K_OUT_ROSA ;

} # END OF INITIALIZE

=====
# (V) ODE EQUATIONS
=====

DYNAMICS {

#SET TEMPERATURE
TC_K = TEMPERATURE + 273.15; # (DEGREE K)
TC_C = TEMPERATURE; # (DEGREE C)

# BODY WEIGHT : DEB GROWTH MODEL ANISOMORPHIC
KT_ARRHENIUS = EXP((TA / TR_DEB) - (TA / TC_K));
DEB_V_T = DEB_V * KT_ARRHENIUS ;
# MM/D
DEB_LM = DEB_V / (DEB_KM * DEB_G);
# MM
DEB_M = POW((DEB_EHM / DEB_EHB), (1.0/3.0));
# EHM AND EHB = J

DT(L) = (DEB_V_T / (3 * (F_CST + DEB_G))) * (F_CST * DEB_M - (L/DEB_LM));
BW = A_BW_L * POW((L/I0)/DEB_SHAPE), (B_BW_L));
# BW = G; A = G/CM; L = MM --> /10 = CM

#VOLUMES (ML OR G) OF THE ORGANS CHANGING WITH THE TIME
V_ART = SC_BLOOD * BW * FRAC_ART_VEN * PLASMA; #BPA IN PLASMA FRACTION
V_VEN = SC_BLOOD * BW * (1-FRAC_ART_VEN) * PLASMA; #BPA IN PLASMA FRACTION

V_LIVER = SC_LIVER * BW;
V_GONADS = SC_GONADS * BW;
V_VISCERA = SC_VISCERA * BW;
V_KIDNEY = SC_KIDNEY * BW;
V_SKIN = SC_SKIN * BW;
V_BRAIN = SC_BRAIN * BW;
V_FAT = SC_FAT * BW;
V_RP = SC_RP * BW;
V_PP = SC_PP * BW;

# BLOOD FLOW (ML/D)
F_CARD_G = F_CARD_REF * EXP((TA / TR_FCARD) - (TA / TC_K)) * POW((BW/BW_FCARD_REF), (-0.1)) ; # CARDIAC OUTPUT = ML/D/G
F_CARD = F_CARD_G * BW * PLASMA; # ML/D OF PLASMA FLOW

# FLOWS TO TISSUES CORRECTED WITH THE UF
F_LIVER = FRAC_LIVER * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_GONADS = FRAC_GONADS * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_VISCERA = FRAC_VISCERA * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_KIDNEY = FRAC_KIDNEY * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_SKIN = FRAC_SKIN * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_FAT = FRAC_FAT * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_BRAIN = FRAC_BRAIN * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;

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F_RP = FRAC_RP * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
F_PP = FRAC_PP * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION;

F_LIVER_GLUCO = FRAC_LIVER * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO;
F_GONADS_GLUCO = FRAC_GONADS * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO;
F_ABDQ_CAVITY_GLUCO = (FRAC_KIDNEY + FRAC_VISCERA) * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO;
F_ROB_GLUCO = (1 - (FRAC_LIVER + FRAC_KIDNEY + FRAC_GONADS + FRAC_VISCERA)) * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO;

F_LIVER_SULFO = FRAC_LIVER * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO;
F_GONADS_SULFO = FRAC_GONADS * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO;
F_ABDQ_CAVITY_SULFO = (FRAC_KIDNEY + FRAC_VISCERA) * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO;
F_ROB_SULFO = (1 - (FRAC_LIVER + FRAC_KIDNEY + FRAC_GONADS + FRAC_VISCERA)) * F_CARD * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO;

# EFFECTIVE RESPIRATORY VOLUME (ML/D)
V_O2_G = V_O2_REF * EXP((TA / TR_VO2) - (TA / TC_K)) * POW((BW/BW_VO2_REF), -0.1); #MG

O2/d/g V_O2 = V_O2_G * BW; # MG

O2/d C_O2_WATER = ((-0.24 * TC_C + 14.04) * SAT) / 1000; # MG O2/ML
F_WATER = V_O2 / (O2_EE * C_O2_WATER); # ML/D
KX = F_WATER; #KX = (TMP < F_WATER ? TMP : F_WATER);

##### BPA CONCENTRATIONS IN TISSUES (MICROG/G = MICROG/ML) #####
C_ART = Q_ART / V_ART;
C_VEN = Q_VEN / V_VEN;
C_LIVER = Q_LIVER / V_LIVER;
C_GONADS = Q_GONADS / V_GONADS;
C_VISCERA = Q_VISCERA / V_VISCERA;
C_KIDNEY = Q_KIDNEY / V_KIDNEY;
C_FAT = Q_FAT / V_FAT;
C_BRAIN = Q_BRAIN / V_BRAIN;
C_SKIN = Q_SKIN / V_SKIN;
C_RP = Q_RP / V_RP;
C_PP = Q_PP / V_PP;

C_TOT = ((Q_ART + Q_VEN + Q_LIVER + Q_GONADS + Q_SKIN + Q_VISCERA + Q_KIDNEY + Q_BRAIN + Q_FAT + Q_RP + Q_PP) / (V_ART + V_VEN + V_LIVER + V_GONADS + V_SKIN + V_VISCERA + V_KIDNEY + V_BRAIN + V_FAT + V_RP + V_PP));

C_TOT_BILE = C_TOT + (Q_BILE/BW); # C_TOT_BILE WITH/WITHOUT Q_BILE/BW
C_CARCASS = (Q_SKIN + Q_BRAIN + Q_FAT + Q_RP + Q_PP) / (V_SKIN + V_BRAIN + V_FAT + V_RP + V_PP);

##### BPA-G CONCENTRATIONS IN TISSUES (MICROG/G = MICROG/ML) #####
C_ART_GLUCO = Q_ART_GLUCO / V_ART;
C_VEN_GLUCO = Q_VEN_GLUCO / V_VEN;
C_LIVER_GLUCO = Q_LIVER_GLUCO / V_LIVER;
C_ABDQ_CAVITY_GLUCO = Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_GLUCO / (V_VISCERA + V_KIDNEY);
C_GONADS_GLUCO = Q_GONADS_GLUCO / V_GONADS;
C_ROB_GLUCO = Q_ROB_GLUCO / (V_SKIN + V_BRAIN + V_FAT + V_RP + V_PP);
C_TOT_GLUCO = ((Q_LIVER_GLUCO + Q_ART_GLUCO + Q_VEN_GLUCO + Q_ROB_GLUCO + Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_GLUCO + Q_GONADS_GLUCO) / (V_ART + V_VEN + V_LIVER + V_GONADS + V_SKIN + V_VISCERA + V_KIDNEY + V_BRAIN + V_FAT + V_RP + V_PP));
C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO = C_TOT_GLUCO + (Q_BILE_GLUCO/BW);

##### BPA-S CONCENTRATIONS IN TISSUES (MICROG/G = MICROG/ML) #####
C_ART_SULFO = Q_ART_SULFO / V_ART;
C_VEN_SULFO = Q_VEN_SULFO / V_VEN;
C_LIVER_SULFO = Q_LIVER_SULFO / V_LIVER;
C_ABDQ_CAVITY_SULFO = Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_SULFO / (V_VISCERA + V_KIDNEY);
C_GONADS_SULFO = Q_GONADS_SULFO / V_GONADS;
C_ROB_SULFO = Q_ROB_SULFO / (V_SKIN + V_BRAIN + V_FAT + V_RP + V_PP);
C_TOT_SULFO = ((Q_LIVER_SULFO + Q_ART_SULFO + Q_VEN_SULFO + Q_ROB_SULFO + Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_SULFO + Q_GONADS_SULFO) / (V_ART + V_VEN + V_LIVER + V_GONADS + V_SKIN + V_VISCERA + V_KIDNEY + V_BRAIN + V_FAT + V_RP + V_PP));
C_TOT_BILE_SULFO = C_TOT_SULFO + (Q_BILE_SULFO/BW);

##### BPA AND METABOLITE CONCENTRATION IN THE WATER : EXPOSURE --> MICROG/G = MICROG/ML #####
# C_WATER = Q_WATER / V_WATER;
# C_WATER_GLUCO = Q_WATER_GLUCO / V_WATER;
# C_WATER_SULFO = Q_WATER_SULFO / V_WATER;

##### SCALING CLEARANCE AND EXCRETION CONSTANT#####
#SCALING CL TO BLOOD VOLUME
CL_SC_PLASMA_GLUCO = CL_PLASMA_GLUCO * V_VEN * UNBOUND_FRACTION;
CL_SC_PLASMA_SULFO = CL_PLASMA_SULFO * V_VEN * UNBOUND_FRACTION;

#SCALING VMAX/CL TO LIVER VOLUME
VMAX_SC_GLUCO = VMAX_GLUCO * V_LIVER;
VMAX_SC_SULFO = VMAX_SULFO * V_LIVER;
#CL_SC_LIVER_GLUCO = CL_LIVER_GLUCO * V_LIVER;
#CL_SC_LIVER_SULFO = CL_LIVER_SULFO * V_LIVER;

#TEMPERATURE CORRECTION
KE_FECES_T = KE_FECES * EXP((TA / TR_EXCRETION) - (TA / TC_K));
KE_BILE_T = KE_BILE * EXP((TA / TR_EXCRETION) - (TA / TC_K));
KE_BILE_GLUCO_T = KE_BILE_GLUCO * EXP((TA / TR_EXCRETION) - (TA / TC_K));
KE_BILE_SULFO_T = KE_BILE_SULFO * EXP((TA / TR_EXCRETION) - (TA / TC_K));

##### BPA METABOLISM #####

#BPA TO BPA-G
DT(Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO) = (VMAX_SC_GLUCO * (C_LIVER/PC_LIVER)) / (KM_GLUCO + (C_LIVER/PC_LIVER));
DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_GLUCO) = CL_SC_PLASMA_GLUCO * C_VEN;
#DT(Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO) = CL_SC_LIVER_GLUCO * (C_LIVER/PC_LIVER);

#BPA TO BPA-S

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DT(Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO) = (VMAX_SC_SULFO * (C_LIVER/PC_LIVER)) / (KM_SULFO + (C_LIVER/PC_LIVER));
DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_SULFO) = CL_SC_PLASMA_SULFO * C_VEN;
#DT(Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO) = CL_SC_LIVER_GLUCO * (C_LIVER/PC_LIVER);

#BPA TOTAL METABOLIZED
DT(Q_MET) = DT(Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO) + DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_GLUCO) + DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_SULFO) + DT(Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO);

##### BPA EXCRETION #####
DT(Q_BILE) = (KE_BILE_T * Q_LIVER * UNBOUND_FRACTION) - EVENT_BILE * K_BG * Q_BILE;

DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS) = KX * (UNBOUND_FRACTION * C_VEN / PC_BLOOD_WATER); #FIXED TO 0 IN MODEL 1 AND 2
DT(Q_LUMEN_GIT) = (- Q_LUMEN_GIT * KE_FECES_T + EVENT_BILE * K_BG * Q_BILE);
DT(Q_EXCRET_FECES) = Q_LUMEN_GIT * KE_FECES_T;
DT(Q_EXCRET) = DT(Q_EXCRET_FECES) + DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS);

##### BPA-G EXCRETION #####
DT(Q_BILE_GLUCO) = (KE_BILE_GLUCO_T * Q_LIVER_GLUCO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO) - EVENT_BILE * K_BG
* Q_BILE_GLUCO;

DT(Q_LUMEN_GIT_GLUCO) = (- Q_LUMEN_GIT_GLUCO * KE_FECES_T + EVENT_BILE * K_BG * Q_BILE_GLUCO);
DT(Q_EXCRET_FECES_GLUCO) = Q_LUMEN_GIT_GLUCO * KE_FECES_T;
DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS_GLUCO) = 0.0; #FIXED TO 0 IN MODEL 1
DT(Q_EXCRET_GLUCO) = DT(Q_EXCRET_FECES_GLUCO) + DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS_GLUCO);

##### BPA-S EXCRETION #####
DT(Q_BILE_SULFO) = (KE_BILE_SULFO_T * Q_LIVER_SULFO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO) - EVENT_BILE * K_BG
* Q_BILE_SULFO;

DT(Q_LUMEN_GIT_SULFO) = (- Q_LUMEN_GIT_SULFO * KE_FECES_T + EVENT_BILE * K_BG * Q_BILE_SULFO);
DT(Q_EXCRET_FECES_SULFO) = Q_LUMEN_GIT_SULFO * KE_FECES_T;
DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS_SULFO) = 0.0; #FIXED TO 0 IN MODEL 1
DT(Q_EXCRET_SULFO) = DT(Q_EXCRET_FECES_SULFO) + DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS_SULFO);

##### BPA ABSORBED : DIFFERENTIALS IN MICROG/D #####
DT(Q_ADMIN_GILLS) = ABS_EFF * KX * C_WATER; #####GILLS

##### BPA BLOOD QUANTITY #####
DT(Q_ART) = (F_CARD * C_VEN * UNBOUND_FRACTION
- F_LIVER * C_ART
- F_KIDNEY * C_ART
- F_VISCERA * C_ART
- F_GONADS * C_ART
- F_SKIN * C_ART
- F_FAT * C_ART
- F_BRAIN * C_ART
- F_RP * C_ART
- F_PP * C_ART);

DT(Q_VEN) = (F_BRAIN * C_BRAIN/PC_BRAIN
+ (F_LIVER + F_GONADS + F_VISCERA + F_RP) * C_LIVER/PC_LIVER
+ F_FAT * C_FAT/PC_FAT
+ (F_KIDNEY + ((1 - A_FPP) * F_PP)
+ ((1 - A_FS) * F_SKIN)) * (C_KIDNEY / PC_KIDNEY)
+ A_FPP * F_PP * (C_PP / PC_PP)
+ A_FS * F_SKIN * (C_SKIN / PC_SKIN)
- F_CARD * C_VEN * UNBOUND_FRACTION
+ DT(Q_ADMIN_GILLS)
- DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS)
- DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_GLUCO)
- DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_SULFO));

##### BPA QUANTITY IN TISSUES #####
DT(Q_GONADS) = F_GONADS * (C_ART - C_GONADS/PC_GONADS);
DT(Q_SKIN) = F_SKIN * (C_ART - C_SKIN /PC_SKIN);
DT(Q_FAT) = F_FAT * (C_ART - C_FAT /PC_FAT);
DT(Q_RP) = F_RP * (C_ART - C_RP /PC_RP);
DT(Q_PP) = F_PP * (C_ART - C_PP /PC_PP);
DT(Q_BRAIN) = F_BRAIN * (C_ART - C_BRAIN /PC_BRAIN);

DT(Q_LIVER) = ( F_LIVER * C_ART
+ F_RP * (C_RP /PC_RP)
+ F_VISCERA * (C_VISCERA /PC_VISCERA)
+ F_GONADS * (C_GONADS /PC_GONADS)
- ( F_LIVER + F_RP + F_VISCERA + F_GONADS ) * (C_LIVER /PC_LIVER)
- KE_BILE_T * Q_LIVER * UNBOUND_FRACTION
- DT(Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO)
- DT(Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO));

DT(Q_KIDNEY) = ( F_KIDNEY * C_ART
+ (1-A_FPP) * F_PP * (C_PP / PC_PP)
+ (1-A_FS) * F_SKIN * (C_SKIN / PC_SKIN)
- (F_KIDNEY + (1-A_FPP) * F_PP + (1-A_FS) * F_SKIN) * (C_KIDNEY /
PC_KIDNEY));

DT(Q_VISCERA) = F_VISCERA * (C_ART - C_VISCERA /PC_VISCERA);

##### BPA-G QUANTITY IN TISSUES #####
DT(Q_ART_GLUCO) = ( F_CARD * C_VEN_GLUCO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO - F_LIVER_GLUCO * C_ART_GLUCO - F_ROB_GLUCO *
C_ART_GLUCO - F_GONADS_GLUCO * C_ART_GLUCO - F_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO * C_ART_GLUCO);
DT(Q_VEN_GLUCO) = ((F_LIVER_GLUCO + F_GONADS_GLUCO) * (C_LIVER_GLUCO/PC_LIVER_GLUCO)
+ (F_ROB_GLUCO * (C_ROB_GLUCO/PC_ROB_GLUCO)
+ (F_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO * (C_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO/PC_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO)
- F_CARD * C_VEN_GLUCO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO
- DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS_GLUCO)
+ (CONV_GLUCO * DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_GLUCO)));

DT(Q_LIVER_GLUCO) = (DT(Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO) * CONV_GLUCO)
+ F_LIVER_GLUCO * C_ART_GLUCO
+ F_GONADS_GLUCO * (C_GONADS_GLUCO /PC_GONADS_GLUCO)

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- (F_LIVER_GLUCO + F_GONADS_GLUCO) * (C_LIVER_GLUCO / PC_LIVER_GLUCO )
- KE_BILE_GLUCO_T * Q_LIVER_GLUCO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO;

DT(Q_ROB_GLUCO)      = F_ROB_GLUCO * (C_ART_GLUCO - (C_ROB_GLUCO/PC_ROB_GLUCO));
DT(Q_GONADS_GLUCO)  = F_GONADS_GLUCO * (C_ART_GLUCO - (C_GONADS_GLUCO/PC_GONADS_GLUCO));
DT(Q_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO) = F_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO * (C_ART_GLUCO - (C_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO/PC_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO));

##### BPA-S QUANTITY IN TISSUES #####

DT(Q_ART_SULFO)      = ( F_CARD * C_VEN_SULFO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO - F_LIVER_SULFO * C_ART_SULFO - F_ROB_SULFO
*C_ART_SULFO - F_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO * C_ART_SULFO - F_GONADS_SULFO * C_ART_SULFO);

DT(Q_VEN_SULFO)      = ((F_LIVER_SULFO + F_GONADS_SULFO) * (C_LIVER_SULFO/PC_LIVER_SULFO))
+ (F_ROB_SULFO * (C_ROB_SULFO/PC_ROB_SULFO))
+ (F_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO * (C_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO/PC_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO))
- F_CARD * C_VEN_SULFO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO
- DT(Q_EXCRET_GILLS_SULFO)
+ (CONV_SULFO * DT(Q_MET_PLASMA_SULFO));

DT(Q_LIVER_SULFO)    = (DT(Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO) * CONV_SULFO)
+ F_LIVER_SULFO * C_ART_SULFO
+ F_GONADS_SULFO * (C_GONADS_SULFO / PC_GONADS_SULFO )
- (F_LIVER_SULFO + F_GONADS_SULFO) * (C_LIVER_SULFO / PC_LIVER_SULFO )
- KE_BILE_SULFO_T * Q_LIVER_SULFO * UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO;

DT(Q_ROB_SULFO)      = F_ROB_SULFO * (C_ART_SULFO - (C_ROB_SULFO/PC_ROB_SULFO));
DT(Q_GONADS_SULFO)  = F_GONADS_SULFO * (C_ART_SULFO - (C_GONADS_SULFO/PC_GONADS_SULFO));
DT(Q_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO) = F_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO * (C_ART_SULFO - (C_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO/PC_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO));

##### CHEMICAL KINETIC IN AQUARIUM WATER #####
#DT(Q_WATER) = (DT(Q_EXCRET) - DT(Q_ELIM_WATER) - DT(Q_ADMIN_GILLS));
#DT(Q_ELIM_WATER) = KE_WATER * Q_WATER ;
#DT(Q_WATER_GLUCO) = DT(Q_EXCRET_GLUCO) ;
#DT(Q_WATER_SULFO) = DT(Q_EXCRET_SULFO) ;

##### SAVE CONCENTRATIONS OF BPA, BPAG AND BPAS AT T = 7D #####
C_TOT_LIND = (T == 7 ? C_TOT_BILE : C_TOT_LIND);
C_TOT_GLUCO_LIND = (T == 7 ? C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO : C_TOT_GLUCO_LIND);
C_TOT_SULFO_LIND = (T == 7 ? C_TOT_BILE_SULFO : C_TOT_SULFO_LIND);

##### TOXICODYNAMIC PART : #####

M_PHAGO = ( (T - TAU) < 1E-12 ? 1 : (1 + (T - TAU) * K_TOL_PHAGO) ) ;
REGULATION = (DELAY > 1E-10 ? ((1/M_PHAGO) * (S_MAX_PHAGO * DELAY)) / (SC_50_PHAGO + DELAY) : 0);
DT(RESPONSE_PHAGO_PERCENT) = K_IN_PHAGO * (1 + REGULATION) - K_OUT_PHAGO * RESPONSE_PHAGO_PERCENT;
DT(DELAY) = KR_DELAY * (C_ART_GLUCO - DELAY);

DT(RESPONSE_MACRO_PERCENT) = K_IN_MACRO * (1 - (C_RP / (EC_50_MACRO + C_RP))) - (K_OUT_MACRO / M_MACRO) * RESPONSE_MACRO_PERCENT;

DT(M_MACRO) = K_TOL_MACRO * RESPONSE_MACRO_PERCENT - K_TOL_MACRO * M_MACRO;

DT(RESPONSE_LYSO) = (K_IN_LYSO / M_LYSO) * (1 + (S_MAX_LYSO * C_RP) / (SC_50_LYSO + C_RP)) - K_OUT_LYSO * RESPONSE_LYSO;

DT(M_LYSO) = K_TOL_LYSO * RESPONSE_LYSO - K_TOL_LYSO * M_LYSO;

DT(RESPONSE_TBARS) = K_IN_TBARS - (K_OUT_TBARS / M_TBARS) * RESPONSE_TBARS * (1 + (S_MAX_TBARS * C_LIVER) / (SC_50_TBARS +
C_LIVER));
DT(M_TBARS) = K_TOL_TBARS * RESPONSE_TBARS - K_TOL_TBARS * M_TBARS;

DT(RESPONSE_ROSA) = K_IN_ROSA * (1 + (S_MAX_ROSA * C_RP) / (SC_50_ROSA + C_RP)) - K_OUT_ROSA * RESPONSE_ROSA;

DT(M_ROSA) = K_TOL_ROSA * RESPONSE_ROSA - K_TOL_ROSA * M_ROSA;
} # END OF DYNAMICS

CALCOUTPUTS{

#CALIBRATION WITH LOG(PREDICTION)
C_TOT = (C_TOT < 0 ? 1E-12 : C_TOT);
C_TOT_BILE = (C_TOT_BILE < 0 ? 1E-12 : C_TOT_BILE);

C_TOT_GLUCO = (C_TOT_GLUCO < 0 ? 1E-12 : C_TOT_GLUCO);
C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO = (C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO < 0 ? 1E-12 : C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO);

C_TOT_SULFO = (C_TOT_SULFO < 0 ? 1E-12 : C_TOT_SULFO);
C_TOT_BILE_SULFO = (C_TOT_BILE_SULFO < 0 ? 1E-12 : C_TOT_BILE_SULFO);

C_BRAIN = (C_BRAIN < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_BRAIN);
C_GONADS = (C_GONADS < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_GONADS);
C_PP = (C_PP < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_PP);

C_ART = (C_ART < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_ART);
C_LIVER = (C_LIVER < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_LIVER);
C_CARCASS = (C_CARCASS < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_CARCASS);

C_ART_GLUCO = (C_ART_GLUCO < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_ART_GLUCO);
C_LIVER_GLUCO = (C_LIVER_GLUCO < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_LIVER_GLUCO);
C_ROB_GLUCO = (C_ROB_GLUCO < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_ROB_GLUCO);

C_ART_SULFO = (C_ART_SULFO < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_ART_SULFO);
C_LIVER_SULFO = (C_LIVER_SULFO < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_LIVER_SULFO);
C_ROB_SULFO = (C_ROB_SULFO < 0 ? 1E-10 : C_ROB_SULFO);

#NEEDED TO CALIBRATE EXCRETION IN LINDHOLST 2003
C_TOT_PC = (C_TOT_LIND > 1E-12 ? C_TOT_BILE / C_TOT_LIND : 1E-12);
C_TOT_GLUCO_PC = (C_TOT_GLUCO_LIND > 1E-12 ? C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO / C_TOT_GLUCO_LIND : 1E-12);
C_TOT_SULFO_PC = (C_TOT_SULFO_LIND > 1E-12 ? C_TOT_BILE_SULFO / C_TOT_SULFO_LIND : 1E-12);

```

```

# MASS-BALANCE

LENGTH = L/DEB_SHAPE ; # PHYSICAL LENGTH (MM)
Q_BODY = (Q_ART + Q_VEN + Q_LIVER + Q_GONADS + Q_BRAIN + Q_FAT + Q_SKIN + Q_KIDNEY + Q_VISCERA +
Q_PP + Q_RP ) ;

Q_ADMIN_TOT = Q_ADMIN_GILLS + IVQUANTITY ; # AMOUNT ENTERING BODY

Q_ELIM_TOT = Q_EXCRET + Q_MET ;

MASS_BAL = Q_ADMIN_TOT - Q_BODY - Q_ELIM_TOT ;
# MASS_BAL_SYS = (Q_ADMIN_TOT - Q_ADMIN_GILLS) - Q_BODY - ( Q_ELIM_TOT - Q_EXCRET) - Q_WATER ;

MASS_BAL_GLUCO = (Q_MET_PLASMA_GLUCO + Q_MET_LIVER_GLUCO) * CONV_GLUCO -
(Q_LIVER_GLUCO+Q_ROB_GLUCO+Q_ART_GLUCO+Q_VEN_GLUCO + Q_LUMEN_GIT_GLUCO + Q_BILE_GLUCO + Q_GONADS_GLUCO + Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_GLUCO) -
Q_EXCRET_GLUCO ;
MASS_BAL_SULFO = (Q_MET_LIVER_SULFO + Q_MET_PLASMA_SULFO) * CONV_SULFO -
(Q_LIVER_SULFO+Q_ROB_SULFO+Q_ART_SULFO+Q_VEN_SULFO + Q_LUMEN_GIT_SULFO + Q_BILE_SULFO + Q_GONADS_SULFO + Q_ABDQ_CAVITY_SULFO) -
Q_EXCRET_SULFO ;

C_BISPHENOL = (C_TOT_BILE + C_TOT_BILE_GLUCO + C_TOT_BILE_SULFO) ;

#TRANSFORMATION FOR CALIBRATION

RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT = RESPONSE_PHAGO_PERCENT/R0_PHAGO ;
RATIO_TBARS = RESPONSE_TBARS/R0_TBARS ;
RATIO_ROSA = RESPONSE_ROSA/R0_ROSA ;
RATIO_MACRO_PERCENT = RESPONSE_MACRO_PERCENT/R0_MACRO ;
RATIO_LYSO = RESPONSE_LYSO/R0_LYSO ;
RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT = (RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT < 0 ? 1E-10 : RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT) ;
RATIO_TBARS = (RATIO_TBARS < 0 ? 1E-10 : RATIO_TBARS) ;
RATIO_ROSA = (RATIO_ROSA < 0 ? 1E-10 : RATIO_ROSA) ;
RATIO_MACRO_PERCENT = (RATIO_MACRO_PERCENT < 0 ? 1E-10 : RATIO_MACRO_PERCENT) ;

RATIO_LYSO = (RATIO_LYSO < 0 ? 1E-10 : RATIO_LYSO) ;

} # END OF CALCOUTPUTS

END.

```

7.2. MCsim input files:

```

### MCMC
### SUBSTANCE : BPA
### BIOMARKERS : PHAGOCYTOSIS (EFFICIENCY) - GRANULOCYTE-MACROPHAGE - LYSOSOMAL PRESENCE - TBARS

### UNITS:
# QUANTITY: MICROG
# VOLUMES: ML
# TIME: D
# FLOWS: ML/D
# CONCENTRATIONS: MICROG/ML
# VMAX: MICROG/D/ ML LIVER
# KM: MICROG/ML
# MASSES: G
# LENGHT: MM
# TEMPERATURE: CELSIUS
# VENTILATION RATE: ML/D

# AUTHORS : CORENTIN MIT
# DATE : 06/2022
# _PHYSIOLOGICAL VLAUES : MALE
#=====

INTEGRATE( LSODES, 1E-8, 1E-10, 1) ;

SETPPOINTS("PHAGOCYTOSIS_BPA.OUT", "TAB_SETPOINT.OUT", 0 ,
K_TOL_PHAGO, S_MAX_PHAGO, SC_50_PHAGO, KR_DELAY, TAU, SIGMA_C_PHAGO) ;

K_IN_PHAGO = 978.69 ;
K_OUT_PHAGO = 37.42 ;
R0_PHAGO = 26.15 ;

#A PRIORI PARAMETER DISTRIBUTIONS
UNBOUND_FRACTION = 0.067 ;
UNBOUND_FRACTION_GLUCO = 0.95 ; # BETWEEN 0 AND 1
UNBOUND_FRACTION_SULFO = 0.95 ; # BETWEEN 0 AND 1

# KM EST EN µMOL/ML ET VMAX EN µG/JOUR/G DE FOIE
KM_GLUCO = 40.0 ;
KM_SULFO = 7.6 ;
RATIO_VMAX_KM_GLUCO = 10.0 ;
RATIO_VMAX_KM_SULFO = 1.5 ;

CL_PLASMA_GLUCO = 38648.1 ;
CL_PLASMA_SULFO = 375.7 ;

RATIO_PC_UF = 4.4 ;
PC_LIVER = 4.8 ;
PC_GONADS = 5.6 ;
PC_VISCERA = 1.1 ; # PARTITION COEF VISCERA FOR BPA
PC_FAT = 0.63 ;

```

```

PC_KIDNEY      = 4.3      ;      # PARTITION COEF KIDNEY FOR BPA
PC_SKIN        = 1.2      ;      # PARTITION COEF SKIN FOR BPA
PC_BRAIN       = 1.9      ;      # PARTITION COEF SKIN FOR BPA
PC_RP = 0.18;
PC_PP = 0.53;

PC_LIVER_GLUCO = 3.3;
PC_ROB_GLUCO = 0.14;
PC_ABDO_CAVITY_GLUCO = 6.89;
PC_GONADS_GLUCO      = 6.92;
KE_BILE_GLUCO = 94.3;

PC_LIVER_SULFO = 3.7;
PC_ROB_SULFO = 0.31;
PC_ABDO_CAVITY_SULFO = 7.46;
PC_GONADS_SULFO      = 7.28;
KE_BILE_SULFO = 62.8;

K_BG      = 1E10 ; # EXCRETED FLOW FROM BILLIARY VESICULE TO FAECES (1/D)
KE_BILE    = 1E-12 ; # EXCRETED FLOW OF BPA FROM LIVER TO BILLIARY VESICULE (1/D)

ABS_EFF = 1.0;
PLASMA = 0.55 ; # STICKLEBACK HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.1242/JEB.065425

#PHAGO
S_MAX_PHAGO = 1.0 ; #DISTRIB(S_MAX_PHAGO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 1.8, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SC_50_PHAGO = 1.0 ; #DISTRIB(SC_50_PHAGO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 0.2, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
K_TOL_PHAGO = 1.0 ; #DISTRIB(K_TOL_PHAGO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 0.1, 0.3, 1E-6, 10.0);
KR_DELAY = 1.0 ; #DISTRIB(KR_DELAY, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 1.0, 0.3, 1E-4, 100.0);
TAU = 1.0 ; #DISTRIB(TAU, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 8.0, 0.3, 7.0, 13.0);

#ROS A
RO_ROSA = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(RO_PHAGO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 27.0, 0.3, 1E-4, 100.0); #MARCHAND ET AL., 2018
K_OUT_ROSA = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(K_OUT_PHAGO, UNIFORM, 1E-6, 1E6);
S_MAX_ROSA = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(S_MAX_PHAGO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 1.8, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SC_50_ROSA = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(SC_50_PHAGO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 0.2, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SIGMA_C_ROSA = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(SIGMA_C_PHAGO, HALFNORMAL, 2);

# # MACROPHAGES
RO_MACRO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(RO_MACRO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 35.0, 0.3, 1E-4, 100.0); #MARCHAND ET AL., 2018
K_OUT_MACRO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(K_OUT_MACRO, UNIFORM, 1E-6, 1E6);
EC_50_MACRO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(EC_50_MACRO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 0.2, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SIGMA_C_MACRO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(SIGMA_C_MACRO, HALFNORMAL, 2);

# # TBARS
RO_TBARS = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(RO_TBARS, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 27.0, 0.3, 1E-4, 100.0); #MARCHAND ET AL., 2018
K_OUT_TBARS = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(K_OUT_TBARS, UNIFORM, 1E-6, 1E6);
S_MAX_TBARS = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(S_MAX_TBARS, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 1.8, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SC_50_TBARS = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(SC_50_TBARS, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 0.2, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);

# # LYSOSOMES
RO_LYSO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(RO_LYSO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 200.0, 0.3, 10, 1E4); #MARCHAND ET AL., 2018
K_OUT_LYSO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(K_OUT_LYSO, UNIFORM, 1E-6, 1E6);
S_MAX_LYSO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(S_MAX_LYSO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 1.8, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SC_50_LYSO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(SC_50_LYSO, TRUNCNORMAL_CV, 0.2, 0.3, 1E-3, 1E3);
SIGMA_C_LYSO = 1.0 ; # DISTRIB(SIGMA_C_LYSO, HALFNORMAL, 2);

SIMULATION { #STICKLEBACK(CONTROL) # SEVEN-DAY EXPOSURE

# PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS
BW_FCARD_REF = 0.294 ; # BODY WEIGHT OF REFERENCE FOR F_CARD FROM EKSTROM, 2016 (PERCH VALUE)
BW_VO2_REF = 0.97 ; # BODY WEIGHT OF REFERENCE FOR VO2 FROM BRAFIELD, 1976 AND WALKLEY, 1970
DEB_V      = 1.26 ; # ENERGY CONDUCTANCE (MM/D) (DEB MODEL PARAMETER)
DEB_G      = 0.7398 ; # ENERGY INVESTMENT RATIO (SU) (DEB MODEL PARAMETER)
DEB_KM     = 0.122 ; # SOMATIC MAINTENANCE RATE COEFFICIENT (1/D) (DEB MODEL PARAMETER)
DEB_EHM    = 1 ; # ENERGY AT STATE OF MATURITY AT METAMORPHOSIS (J)
DEB_EHB    = 1 ; # ENERGY AT STATE OF MATURITY AT BIRTH (J)
DEB_SHAPE  = 0.247 ;
A_BW_L     = 0.01543825 ; # = (0.249^3), # BW= A*TL^B PARAMETER (MG/MM)
B_BW_L     = 3.0 ; # B RELATION BW(MG)=F(L(MM)) --> SU

# ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITION
TA          = 6130 ; # ARRHENIUS TEMPERATURE IN KELVIN
TR_DEB     = 293.65 ; # (KELVIN)
TR_FCARD   = 289.15 ; # (KELVIN) -> TEMPERATURE OPTIMAL : 16 C
TR_VO2     = 283.15 ; # (KELVIN)
TR_EXCRETION = 289.15 ; # (KELVIN)

# EFFECTIVE RESPIRATORY VOLUME & CARDIAC OUTPUT
F_CARD_REF = 62.96969 ; # = Qb_REF_PERCH * (BW_REF^(0.75)) / BW_REF # (ML/D/G) = 46.368 *
(0.294^(0.75)) / 0.294 --> ALLOMETRIC SCALLING FUNCTION FROM EKSTROM,2016
V_O2_REF   = 4.03 ; # REFERENCE OXYGEN COMSUPTION RATE (MG O2/G/D) --> FROM BRAFIELD, 1976
O2_EE      = 0.71 ; # OXYGEN EXTRACTION EFFICIENCY OF 71% PROPOSED BY ERICKSON, 1990
SAT         = 0.90 ; # DISSOLVED OXYGEN SATURATION OF 90% PROPOSED BY ERICKSON, 1990

# VOLUME SCALING FACTOR : FRACTION OF BW (%)
SC_BLOOD   = 0.009 ;
SC_GONADS  = 0.00781598 ;
SC_BRAIN   = 0.012 ;
SC_LIVER   = 0.053860073 ;
SC_FAT     = 0.0168 ;
SC_SKIN    = 0.036 ;
SC_VISCERA = 0.055 ;
SC_KIDNEY  = 0.011725124 ;
SC_RP      = 0.032 ;

# FRACTION OF ARTERIAL BLOOD FLOW
FRAC_GONADS = 0.0054 ;
FRAC_BRAIN  = 0.0392 ;
FRAC_LIVER  = 0.0529 ;

```



```

0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.0049,0.000
25 ,

0,0.0416666666666667,0.0833333333333333,0.125,0.166666666666667,0.2083333333333333,0.25,0.291666666666667,0.3
3333333333333333,0.375,0.416666666666667,0.4583333333333333,0.5,0.541666666666667,0.5833333333333333,0.625,0.666666666666667,0.7083333333333333,0.75,0.791666666666667,0.8333333333333333,0.875,0.916666666666667,0.9583333333333333,1,1.04166666
666667,1.0833333333333333,1.125,1.166666666666667,1.2083333333333333,1.25,1.291666666666667,1.3333333333333333,1.375,1.416666
66666667,1.4583333333333333,1.5,1.541666666666667,1.5833333333333333,1.625,1.666666666666667,1.7083333333333333,1.75,1.791666
66666667,1.8333333333333333,1.875,1.916666666666667,1.9583333333333333,2,2.041666666666667,2.0833333333333333,2.125,2.16666666
666667,2.2083333333333333,2.25,2.291666666666667,2.3333333333333333,2.375,2.416666666666667,2.4583333333333333,2.5,2.54166666
666667,2.5833333333333333,2.625,2.666666666666667,2.7083333333333333,2.75,2.791666666666667,2.8333333333333333,2.875,2.916666
66666667,2.9583333333333333,3,3.041666666666667,3.0833333333333333,3.125,3.166666666666667,3.2083333333333333,3.25,3.29166666
666667,3.3333333333333333,3.375,3.416666666666667,3.4583333333333333,3.5,3.541666666666667,3.5833333333333333,3.625,3.66666666
666667,3.7083333333333333,3.75,3.791666666666667,3.8333333333333333,3.875,3.916666666666667,3.9583333333333333,4,4.04166666
666667,4.0833333333333333,4.125,4.166666666666667,4.2083333333333333,4.25,4.291666666666667,4.3333333333333333,4.375,4.41666666
666667,4.4583333333333333,4.5,4.541666666666667,4.5833333333333333,4.625,4.666666666666667,4.7083333333333333,4.75,4.79166666
666667,4.8333333333333333,4.875,4.916666666666667,4.9583333333333333,5,5.041666666666667,5.0833333333333333,5.125,5.16666666
666667,5.2083333333333333,5.25,5.291666666666667,5.3333333333333333,5.375,5.416666666666667,5.4583333333333333,5.5,5.54166666
666667,5.5833333333333333,5.625,5.666666666666667,5.7083333333333333,5.75,5.791666666666667,5.8333333333333333,5.875,5.916666
666667,5.9583333333333333,6,6.041666666666667,6.0833333333333333,6.125,6.166666666666667,6.2083333333333333,6.25,6.29166666
666667,6.3333333333333333,6.375,6.416666666666667,6.4583333333333333,6.5,6.541666666666667,6.5833333333333333,6.625,6.66666666
666667,6.7083333333333333,6.75,6.791666666666667,6.8333333333333333,6.875,6.916666666666667,6.9583333333333333,7,7.04166666
666667,7.0833333333333333 );

#EXPERIMENTAL DATA
PRINTSTEP(RESPONSE_PHAGO_PERCENT, 0, 14, 0.05);
PRINTSTEP(RATIO_PHAGO_PERCENT, 0, 14, 0.05);
PRINTSTEP(C_RP, 0, 14, 0.05);
}

END.

```

7.3. tab_setpoint.out

```

K_TOL_PHAGO.1. S_MAX_PHAGO.1. SC_50_PHAGO.1. KR_DELAY.1. TAU.1. SIGMA_C_PHAGO.1.
0.980969 0.215426 0.127866 0.841498 12.1557 1.10211
0.980969 0.362681 0.127866 0.841498 11.7805 1.10211
0.74399 0.362681 0.127866 0.841498 11.7805 1.11414
0.670547 0.362681 0.099472 1.29955 11.7805 1.11137
0.552054 0.269903 0.088233 1.29955 11.7805 1.11736
0.566126 0.358806 0.088233 1.29955 10.7693 1.10922
0.566126 0.327516 0.088233 1.29955 12.3661 1.11079
0.64649 0.1897 0.0648158 1.29955 12.9026 1.10179
0.480384 0.252511 0.0550445 1.29955 12.9573 1.10519
0.480384 0.252511 0.126588 1.29955 10.0259 1.10519
0.248284 0.252511 0.0516114 1.29955 10.0259 1.11711
0.248284 0.252511 0.0516114 1.29955 10.0259 1.1144
0.369525 0.252511 0.0528741 1.29955 9.7715 1.1144
0.369525 0.252511 0.0528741 1.29955 9.7715 1.11075
0.369525 0.21298 0.0828182 1.29955 9.7715 1.11075
0.243819 0.21298 0.0828182 1.29955 9.7715 1.11711
0.243819 0.254703 0.0828182 1.29955 9.7715 1.11711
0.243819 0.254703 0.0828182 1.29955 9.7715 1.1109
0.286479 0.285945 0.0828182 1.29955 9.7715 1.10491
0.520976 0.285945 0.0828182 1.29955 11.4773 1.11723
0.521397 0.254066 0.0828182 1.29955 11.4773 1.10544
0.563571 0.254066 0.0828182 1.29955 11.4773 1.10544
0.626506 0.254066 0.0828182 1.29955 11.4773 1.11938
0.776005 0.254066 0.0974643 1.29955 11.4773 1.11226
0.776005 0.254066 0.0974643 1.10119 11.4773 1.10348
0.698628 0.254066 0.0974643 1.10119 11.4773 1.10348
0.495041 0.254066 0.1197 1.10119 11.4773 1.10726
0.548764 0.254066 0.1197 1.10119 11.4773 1.10476
0.556748 0.339658 0.0940046 1.10119 10.1922 1.10476
0.556748 0.274329 0.0940046 1.10119 10.1922 1.10202
0.765615 0.25802 0.0940046 1.19235 10.1922 1.11361
0.767867 0.25802 0.0940046 1.24257 10.1922 1.11361
0.682536 0.25802 0.0443906 1.24257 10.1922 1.11361
0.776613 0.25802 0.0443906 1.24257 10.1922 1.11361
MVP 0.860222 0.276636 0.0983165 1.00413 12.3328 1.10006

```

8. References

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